

Fabric Printing Design: An Inspiration from Thai Kites

Suwit Sadsunk

Abstract—This research paper was aimed to study different motifs found on Thai kites in order to be create new fabric printing designs. The objectives of the study were (1) to examine different motifs of Thai kites; and (2) to create appropriate printing designs for fabric based on an examination of motifs of Thai kites from primary and secondary sources. The study found that designs, motifs and colors found on Thai kites were various based on individual artisans' imagination in each period. From the historical review, there have been 4 kinds of Thai kites namely I-Loom Kite, Pak Pao Kite, Chula Kite and Dui Dui Kite. Nowadays, the kite designs have been developed to be more various by shape and color such as snake-shaped kite, owl-shaped kite and peacock-shaped kite.

Keywords—Thai Kites, Fabric Printing Design.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE lifestyle of people has changed through the course of time and therefore a diversity of values have occurred. Modern technology has transformed slow lifestyles to faster pace. The development has added a variety of things to the world; thus traditional Thai values and wisdoms have constrained to survive. Therefore, it is sometime necessary to revitalize old wisdoms so that they may live on in this changing world. Local wisdoms of Thailand are characterized by their distinctive beauty and interpretation. Thai kites can be considered a Thai handicraft that reflects unique local wisdoms that vary according to different regions. Materials used in inventing a kite can be found locally and mostly come from nature. People invented kites for local sport and recreation for children and people in general, usually for playing during leisure time. Kite-flying has been common in Thailand as a competition. Thai kites thus represent special knowledge which should be preserved and passed on from generation to generation. Creating a kit is not only making the structure but also creating its distinctive character through design and motif. Craftsmanship of making a kite nowadays is disappearing due to less popularity and the fact that there are a few people to carry on the tradition. Consequently, some types of Thai kites are disappearing [1].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kite-flying has been known as a recreation among Thai people for more than 700 years since Sukhothai period. The recreation has been carried on until Rattanakosin period, in which people from all social status from royal families to general population. Thai kites have thus acquired a national

Mr.Suwit Sadsunk is a lecturer at the Faculty of Fine and Applied Arts, Fashion Design at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (phone: 06621601388; fax: 06621601199; e-mail: suwit.sa@ssru.ac.th).

unique form [2]. Four kinds of Thai kites were common seen in flying including I- Loom Kite, Pak Pao Kite, Chula Kite and Dui Dui Kite. Animal-shaped kites have also been found during these days. The most common materials for making a kite are bamboo and light paper. Making a kite requires delicate craftsmanship especially in making Chula and Pak Pao Kites where the knowledge of selecting the most ideal bamboo is needed for strong structure [3]. Because Thai kites represent special knowledge that should be preserved and passed on from generations to generations, the objectives of this study were (1) to examine different motifs of Thai kites by their designs, patterns and colors; and (2) to create appropriate printing designs for fabric based on an examination of motifs of Thai kites. The creativity from this research was deliberately designed to reflect an exquisite combination of beauty of the past and of the present.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is a creative research and the methodology is illustrated in Fig. 1. The primary data was gathered from the focus-group interviews while the secondary data was collected from various sources relevant to Thai kites in terms of artistic and historical background such as museums, toyshops and Thai Kite museums. The findings were used as an inspiration for creating contemporary printing designs for fabric product

Fig. 1 Methodology

IV. FINDINGS

A. Shapes and Designs

Fig. 2 displays different kinds of Thai kites presenting individual shapes and designs. These include, for example, Chula Kite, Pak Pao Kite, Dui Dui Kite, I- Loom Kite, I- Prad Kite, and other kites in the shape of buffalo, butterfly and peacock. Mostly the kites have animal shapes [4].

Fig. 2 Shapes and Designs of Thai Kites

B. Patterns, Motifs and Colors

Patterns, motifs and colors of Thai kites vary by regions as show in Fig. 3. Craftsmen fashion them in many different ways.

Fig. 3 Patterns, Motifs and Colors of Thai Kites

C. Creation of Appropriate Printing Designs for Fabric Based On an Examination of Motifs of Thai kites

The procedure of creating printing designs for fabric was implemented based on the art composition of decorative designs for example: point, line, color, light and shade, balance, repetition, movement and dominance or emphasis [5] (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Creation of appropriate printing designs for fabric based on an examination of motifs of Thai kites

D. End Product: The Printing Designs for Fabric Demonstrated by 2 Patterns

Pattern I (Fig. 5)

The first fabric pattern is illustrated in Figs. 5 and 6. This was designed using the four-way layout in making the pattern, using the square shape. The four-way layout is a design in which motifs face all four directions, for example, up, down, left, and right. The art composition such as repetition technique was also applied, using touching technique [6]

Fig. 5 Pattern I

Classification of Pattern I (Fig. 6)

Thai kites which can be classified as suitable model for creating Pattern I include Chula Kite, Butterfly-shaped Kite, Owl-shaped Kite, Snake-shaped Kite, Peacock-shaped Kite and Buffalo-shaped Kite. The circular cylinder shape for coiling the kite's string was also added as a decorative element on the frame of the pattern. The background presents fish and star motifs of Chula Kite. The colors utilized are associated with liveliness and fun.

Fig. 6 Classification of Pattern I

Pattern II (Fig. 7)

The second fabric pattern created is illustrated in Figs. 7 and 8. This pattern was designed using the two-way layout, using the circular shape. The two-way layout is a design which shows motifs in reversal fashion. The intersection technique was also applied, making all motifs connected to each other [7].

Fig. 7 Pattern II

Classification of Pattern II (Fig. 8)

Thai kites which can be classified as suitable model for creating Pattern II include Chula Kite, Butterfly- shaped Kite, Owl- shaped Kite, Snake- shaped Kite, Peacock- shaped Kite, and Pak Pao Kite. The background presents floral, fish and star motifs of Chula Kite. The colors utilized are associated with delicate, feminine and springtime, such as Pastel. This pattern is a perfect choice for designing women scarves or tippets.

Fig. 8 Classification of Pattern II

IV. DISCUSSION

This creative research was conducted in order to create appropriate printing designs for fabric based on an examination of Thai kites in terms of history, common designs and colors, and materials from different regions of Thailand. The findings were analyzed and the two fabric patterns were designed as the end product, where the art composition was applied for the purposes of form and function. The patterns were purposely designed for printing on fabric for further production of 120 x 120 cm. scarf or tippet. The creativity contributed from this research's findings is an inspiration for an extension of product development in textile business sector in the future, which will be a contemporary value for both Thai and international fashion clothing and textile design industry [6].

V. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The limitation of this study concerns the fact that only some popular and commonly- seen types of Thai kites were selected for the analysis and the development of the end product. Further research may consider other kinds of Thai kites which have their own unique characteristics to be applied in creating new fabric patterns. Another limitation included a low variety of sites for fieldwork due to time limitation. Additional studied should emphasize in-depth interviews with kite inventors, reviews of various websites and documents relevant to Thai kites, including museums exhibiting stories of Thai kites.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank the Research and Development Institute, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand for their financial support and assistance. The author would also like to thank Mr. Kevin Wongleedee, Director of Centre for ASEAN Studies and Research, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University for assisting in proofreading the manuscript and providing an important suggestion to this research paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] Office of the National Culture Commission, Ministry of Culture, Thailand, Thai kite: a local Thai recreation for summer (Book style), May, 2012.
- [2] Wat Samrong, Nakorn Pathom, The history of Thai kites (Book style), Nakorn Pathom, January, 2012.
- [3] Pinyo Suwankreeree, "The legend of Thai kites (Unpublished work style)," May, 2012.
- [4] Niyom KhonSue, The Handcrafted Kites of Thailand (Book style), Bangkok: Petchkarat Printing, 1994.
- [5] Oythip Pholsri, Pattern designs (Book style), Bangkok: Odeon Store, 2002.
- [6] Atcharaporn Sailasut, Fabric pattern designs and printing techniques (Book style), Bangkok: Sahaprachaphanich Printing, 1981.
- [7] Department of Industrial Promotion, Ministry of Industry, Thailand, Fabric printing (Book style), 1981.